

The residue, insoluble in ether and hot water was recrystallised from alcohol. It was identified as 3-nitro-4-methoxycinnamic acid. m. p. 244°-45° (Found : C, 53.99; H, 4.04; N, 6.03 per cent. Calc. for $C_{10}H_9O_5N$: C, 53.81; H, 4.03; N, 6.28 per cent).

The above procedure was repeated under various conditions (Table 1).

The 3-nitro-4-methoxycinnamic acid obtained was reduced by the method of Pettit and Neill³ using ethanol as the solvent. m. p. 222-4°. Yield 33% (Found : C, 61.97; H, 5.67; N, 7.11 per cent. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$: C, 62.18; H, 5.7; N, 7.25 per cent).

The amine was characterised by preparing the acetyl, benzoyl and sulphamido derivatives (Table 2).

References

1. T. JOHNSON and E. KOHMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **37**, 162.
2. G. SINGH SIDHU, et al, *Ann.*, 1959, **627**, 218.
3. G. PETTIT and A. NEILL, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 1764.
4. K. PANDYA and T. VAHIDY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **4A**, 134.
5. HEILBRON and BUNBURY, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds'. 1953 ed., Vol. 3, p. 630.
6. T. SABALITSCHKA and K. TIEDGE, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, **272**, 384; *Chem. Abs.*, 1934, **28**, 3836.
7. T. MURAI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1961, **34**, 178; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 15444.

Use of 2-Hydroxy-4-*n*-Propoxy Acetophenone Oxime (HPaox) as Analytical Reagent Gravimetric Determination of Nickel

S. M. PATEL and H. B. NAIK

Chemistry Department, M. R. Science Institute, Gujarat College, Ahmedabad-380006

Manuscript received 15 January 1975; accepted 12 February 1975

2-Hydroxy-4-*n*-propoxy acetophenone oxime (HPAOX) has been found to be a suitable chelating agent for gravimetric determination of nickel. The reagent reacts quantitatively with Ni(II) in the pH range 5.0 to 9.0 giving insoluble metal complex. The green nickel complex can be directly weighed as $Ni(C_{11}H_{14}O_3N)_2$ after drying at 110°-120°. The Ni(II) has been determined gravimetrically at pH 5.5, the error being less than $\pm 0.4\%$. The interference due to several ions such as Ca(II), Ba(II), Zn(II), Mg(II), Co(II), Fe(III) have been avoided by working at controlled pH and by using suitable masking agent. The reagent was prepared from 2-hydroxy-4-*n*-propoxy acetophenone and crystallised from petroleum ether, colourless needles, m.p. 84° (Found N, 6.6 and calculated N, 6.7%).

The nickel bischelate (Ni calculated 12.37%, found 12.33%) with the reagent precipitated at pH 5.5 is green coloured and is insoluble in water, ethanol, ether and dil. acetic acid but it is soluble in chloroform.

Procedure for the determination of Ni(II) : An aliquot standard solution of Ni(II) was diluted to 200 ml and pH was adjusted using acetate buffer. The solution was warmed to 60°-70° and 1% ethanolic solution (10% excess) of the reagent was added with constant stirring. The precipitate was heated at 60°-70° and allowed to stand for about 30 min. It was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G 4); washed with ethanol to remove excess reagent, dried at 110°-120° to constant weight. The conversion factor of nickel/nickel complex is 0.1237. The results of some of the estimations are given below

Determination of nickel

Ni(II) (taken) in mg	Ni(II) (found) in mg	% error
8.91	8.90	-0.11
14.85	14.84	-0.07
29.70	29.69	+0.34
44.55	44.53	-0.04
59.40	59.37	-0.05

Determination of nickel in Presence of other ions : Nickel(II) was determined in presence of Ca(II), Ba(II), Zn(II), Mg(II), at pH 5.5 as these ions were found to give no colour formation or insoluble chelate.

Co(II) gives orange yellow precipitate at pH 6.5 but cobalt chelate is soluble in ethanol. It was therefore possible to determine Ni(II), at pH 5.5 in the presence of Co(II). The maximum error is $\pm 0.2\%$.

The presence of Fe(III) interferes during the determination of Ni(II). However, the determination was carried out by sequestering the Fe(III) by potassium tartrate. (maximum error is $\pm 0.3\%$).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. V. M. Thakor for his keen interest and helpful suggestions in this work and to Principal, Gujarat College, Ahmedabad for providing all necessary facilities.

Reference

1. EIJKMAN, BERGEMA, AND HENRARD, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, **1**, 815.

Studies in Terpenes. Part XLI : Synthesis of Terpinolene

C. PUNNOOSE MATHEW and JAMES VERGHESE
Department of Chemistry, Christian Medical College,
Vellore-632002

Manuscript received 21 April 1975; accepted 29 May 1975

THIS paper describes a simple synthesis of terpinolene (I) from the readily available d-limonene (II). d-Limonene dihydrobromide (III) obtained by hydrobromination¹ of (II), upon bromination under ultraviolet irradiation² provided 1,4,8-tribromo-*p*-menthane

(IV).⁸ By reaction with zinc/ethanol⁴, (IV) led to 1-bromo-*p*-menth-4(8)-ene (V) and the latter was selectively dehydrobrominated to (I) using silver nitrate-dimethyl sulphoxide reagent⁵.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Pmr spectra are in carbon tetrachloride and ir spectra are from thin film. Glc was run on an SE-30 column.

1,8-Dibromo-*p*-menthane(III): d-Limonene was converted into (III) adopting Wallach's procedure;¹ m.p. and mixed m.p. 64°.

1,4,8-Tribromo-*p*-menthane(IV): A clear solution of the dibromoderivative (III) (20 g) in carbon tetrachloride (120 ml) was brominated under ultraviolet irradiation.² Evaporation of the solvent followed by crystallisation from ethyl acetate-methanol gave (IV) (18 g), m.p. 110°, (lit.² 109-110°); (Found: Br, 63.36 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇Br₃: Br, 63.66 per cent).

1-Bromo-*p*-menth-4(8)-ene (V): To a vigorously stirred suspension of (IV) (14 g), in dry ether (70 ml) and absolute ethanol (14 ml) at 0-5°, zinc dust (2.42 g) was added and the stirring continued for 13 hr. (It was observed that excessive cooling resulted in slow and partial debromination). The resulting clear solution was washed with water till free of bromide ion and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of ether under suction followed by recrystallisation from methanol afforded (V) (5.53 g), m.p. 34°-35°, (lit.⁴ 34-35°); (Found: Br, 37.6 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇Br: Br, 37.2 per cent); pmr: δ 1.65 (s, 6H, CH₃-C=C), 1.8 (s, 3H, CH₃-C-Br), 2.01 (m, 4H, -CH₂-C=C), 2.31 (m, 4H, -CH₂-C-Br); ir: 2960, 2920, 2862, 1630, 1440, 1370, 770 cm⁻¹.

1,4(8)-*p*-Menthadlene (I): The monobromide (V) (5.53 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (23 ml) was stirred with a solution of silver nitrate (4.33 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (20 ml) at ~30° for 2 hr. The precipitated silver chloride was removed by filtration, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°)(15 ml) and the filtrate extracted with petroleum ether (10×5 ml), washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent stripped by evaporation. Vacuum distillation of the oil received yielded homogeneous terpinolene (1.8 g); glc: single peak; b.p. 120°-121°/100 mm; n_D²⁰ 1.4861; (Found: C, 88.49; H, 11.51 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₆: C, 88.16; H,

11.84 per cent); pmr: δ 1.6 (broad, 9H, CH₃-C=C), 1.9 (m, 2H, -CH₂-C=C), 2.2 (m, 2H, -CH₂-C=) 2.6 (m, 2H, =C-CH₂-C=) and 5.25 (m, 1H, -CH=C); ir: 2960, 2920, 2862, 1630, 1440, 1370, 790 cm⁻¹; tetrabromide m.p. and mixed m.p. 116°.

References

1. O. WALLACH, *Annalen*, 1887, 239, 12.
2. R. M. BOWMAN, A. CHAMBERS and W. R. JACKSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1966, 1297.
3. O. WALLACH, *Annalen*, 1891, 264, 25.
4. A. BAEYER and F. BLAU, *Chem. Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2291
5. B. SINGARAM and J. VERGHESE, (in press)

Stability Constants of Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime with Ni(II), Co(II) Zn(II) and Mn(II)

B. H. PATEL, J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388120, Gujarat

Manuscript received 4 April 1975; accepted 13 June 1975

THIS communication reports the investigations of stability constants of complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime with Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) by Calvin-Bjerrum technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti¹ at 40° ($\mu \approx 0.1M$ NaClO₄) in water-dioxane (25 : 75 v/v) medium.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime was prepared by the aqueous ethanolic alkali method from ketone. Its stock solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount in purified dioxane² (S. Merck technical grade). All solutions and pH-measurements were made as described earlier³.

Three titrations, viz. titration of (i) free perchloric acid, (ii) free perchloric acid plus the reagent and (iii) free acid plus the reagent plus the metal ion, were done against standard NaOH.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that \bar{n}_H values did not fall in to the range 0 to 1, indicating that either the hydrogen of oximino group did not dissociate or its dissociation overlapped the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen. Assuming the later possibility an attempt was made to evaluate the two constants ${}^pK^{H_1}$ and K^{H_2} by the method of least squares⁴. It gives a negative value for the product of ${}^pK^{H_1} \cdot {}^pK^{H_2}$, however ${}^pK^{H_2}$ is positive. Therefore, it was concluded that only the phenolic-OH is dissociated. Thus 2-hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime was considered monobasic and the \bar{n}_H values accordingly were reduced by 1. The practical proton-ligand stability constant, $\log {}^pK^H$, has been obtained as the Bjerrum half-integral value. The same has also been calculated at different points using the equation

$$\log {}^pK^{H=B} + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H}$$

The average value of $\log {}^pK^H$ (9.20) obtained by the pointwise calculation is in good agreement with the half-integral value (Table 1).